

Effects of the Lifestyle Modification Program on Blood BDNF and Its Associated Factors in Korean Collegiate Students

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Background: Multiple epidemiological studies have documented that both vegetarian diet and moderate exercise indicate various mental and physical health benefits, respectively, but the combined effects of the both interventions on mental health have not been extensively studied yet.

Aim: To clarify the combined effects of a vegetarian diet and physical activities on mental and physical health, we tried to analyze the influence of the physical exercise program and regular vegetarian diet for 10 days on blood brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) level, mood status, and physical fitness factors by the profile of mood states (POMS) test in Korean collegiate students.

Methods: A total of 54 Korean collegiate students ($M_{age} = 18.0 \pm 1.0$ years) including 36 men and 18 women were included in this study. They performed the regular physical activity program with vegetarian diets and were staying at the residential building together for a total of 10 days. Variables including body composition, physical fitness factors, POMS score, and blood BDNF level were measured twice before and after the intervention.

Results: Our program showed the beneficial effects of improvement of physical fitness and weight loss. Especially, the blood BDNF level was significantly increased in the both females ($t = -2.761, p = .013$) and male students after the intervention ($t = -3.392, p = .002$), respectively, suggesting the beneficial contribution of this intervention on the mental health of Korean collegiate students.

Conclusion: These data suggest that our program may be a useful tool for the mental and physical health improvement of Korean collegiate students. Further studies using larger sample sizes will be needed to replicate the health-benefit effect of this intervention.

Relationship Between Sport Participation Motivation and Teaching Games for Understanding Among Novice Handball Players

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The teaching games for understanding (TGfU) approach breaks games skills down into step-by-step movements

that allow students to be more successful at complicated skills. As students begin to develop their skills in a given task, it can increase the amount of active participation and "promote enjoyment for participants." Some research suggests that TGfU is an effective approach to increasing fun in sport. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the relationship between sport participation motivation and the TGfU approach among novice handball players. We compared motivation to participate in sport in a group of 19 student novice handball players (aged 10–12 years old) in Tehran City, Iran, who have been trained in the TGfU approach for 3 months, to 20 participants who have been trained based on a traditional technique-based approach for the same time period. We used the Sport Participation Motivation Questionnaire for evaluation of sport participation motivation status of the participants. An independent *t* test was used to compare sport participation motivation level between the 2 groups. The results revealed a significant difference between the 2 groups in sport participation motivation level: The TGfU group had significantly higher sport participation motivation compared with the other group ($p < .05$).

Effect of the TGfU Approach on Motor Development and Social Maturity of Elementary School Students

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The teaching games for understanding (TGfU) approach was developed to tap into children's inherent desire to play. If TGfU, as a new pedagogical model in physical education (PE), is to become a movement that will broaden the scope of PE, it must be anchored in sound research that explores its influences on different domains. Of significant importance in the delivery of learning opportunities within a TGfU structure is the notion that it has the potential to enhance development of psychomotor, cognitive, affective, and social skills. The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of the TGfU approach in soccer on the motor and social development of Grade 4 elementary school students (10 years old) compared to the technique-based approach. Two Grade 4 classes (each 15 students) from an elementary school in Tehran City, Iran, were selected as the experimental and control groups. The experimental group was followed for 10 soccer units, which were taught using the TGfU approach in 5 weeks (2 sessions per week). At the same time, the control group was trained based on a traditional technique-based

